

Conformity report of IPBES assessments with the data and knowledge management policy;

- **Methodological assessment regarding the diverse conceptualization of multiple values of nature and its benefits, including biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services**
- **Thematic assessment of the sustainable use of wild species of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services**

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Highlights

- The overall score of the Values assessment was: 72.4% and the overall score of the Sustainable Use assessment was 69.2%.
- Good compliance of the delivery of chapters and supplementary materials, disclaimers and delivery of data and knowledge from Indigenous people and local communities
- Need of improvement on the delivery of figures and tables, in particular, on the delivery of interoperable figures and original machine-readable data, the inclusion of the doi in the caption of figures and tables and the upload of workflows or scripts used to create figures
- Several quick and small improvements can increase the overall score of the Sustainable Use assessment to 76.7% and the overall score of the Values assessment to 77.2%
- In order to implement the FAIR principles, a complete author's list, original data files and workflows or scripts are indispensable

Rationale

To ensure that the assessments are delivered in agreement with the IPBES data and knowledge management policy, the delivery protocol for assessment drafts was created. An objective scorecard was designed to determine how well this protocol is followed. The Values and Sustainable Use assessments were then scored following this scorecard. This report provides valuable insights on how well the IPBES data and knowledge management policy is currently implemented in IPBES products, and it highlights areas where the delivery protocol for assessment drafts could be improved.

Introduction

The first IPBES data management policy was published in 2020, after being approved by the MEP and Bureau meeting in January of that year. The IPBES delivery protocol of the assessment drafts was developed to assist the technical support units of the assessments with the implementation of the policy in their products. The protocol is a guideline for technical support units when preparing their milestone drafts to the Secretariat. The policy and delivery protocol are designed to be regularly updated, with the most recent revisions published in 2022 (data and knowledge management policy: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3551078>; delivery protocol of the assessment drafts: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6225417>).

To monitor the implementation of the policy within the Platform, the task force on knowledge and data requested its technical support unit to conduct a qualitative analysis of how well recently published IPBES assessments adhere to the policy, and to report the findings.

An objective scorecard was designed to 'score' each assessment on how well they complied to the delivery of the drafts protocol, and thereby to the data and knowledge management policy. The findings will give an insight into the performance of the assessments as well as show which (sub)sections of the policy and protocol are causing difficulties for the assessment TSUs. The technical support unit on data will use these findings to propose a revised version of the delivery of the assessment drafts protocol and provide adjusted support to the assessment TSUs.

Results

The overall score of the Values assessment was: 72.4% and the overall score of the Sustainable Use assessment was 69.2%. The score of each of the subsections is broken down.

Citation: both assessments scored 80% for the citations section, as the authors lists of both were incomplete; the Values assessment did not include any lead authors for their first chapter and no review editors for the first and second chapter. The authors list for the Sustainable Use assessment contained some mistakes in the names of the authors. For both assessments it was found that the countries of residence and

affiliation were sometimes wrong or incomplete. Additionally, the provided authors lists were different from the assessment authors mentioned on the IPBES website and from the authors as they appear in the suggested citations for the chapters. All the other requirements regarding the citations of the assessment chapters, full report and SPM were met.

Bibliographic references: The Values assessment scored 83.3% and Sustainable Use scored 50%. Both assessments had their own library in Zotero, and separate folders for each chapter, and all references were, as required, in APA 7th edition style. Additionally, the references for the Values assessment were entered in the right Zotero folders, and in-text citations were complete and unbroken. Both assessments failed to delete unused references from their reference lists, and not all entries had an identifier. For this, books were not taken into consideration, as isbn numbers are not added to the reference lists when APA 7th edition style is applied, so only the materials that should have an accompanying identifier or url were taken into account.

Chapters and supplementary material: The Values assessment scored 85.7% for this section, as they provided all these items, although data management reports were not uploaded as such, but as part of the supplementary material uploaded to Zenodo. However, some of the annexes were missing on Zenodo. The Sustainable Use assessment received the same score (85.7%), as they did not export a bibliography to Zenodo yet.

Figures: The Values assessment scored 57.9% and the Sustainable Use assessment scored 68.4% on the delivery of their figures. The main issues were: missing identifiers in the captions of the original, borrowed and adapted figures, unfulfilled requirement that country names follow the ISO 3166-1 alpha 3 code, and the incomplete upload of documentation on the workflow or scripts used to create the figures to Zenodo. The Values assessment further used maps with country borders (without a disclaimer explaining the reasoning behind the borders) and did not always include the proper citation from the borrowed figures in the reference list or assign the usage rights to borrowed or adapted figures. For the Sustainable Use assessment no interoperable figures were uploaded to Zenodo.

Tables: Both assessments did not upload original machine-readable data underlying the table along with their caption; although many csv files were uploaded for the Values assessment, their captions did not relate to the table names and numbers in the chapters, and identifiers were lacking from the captions. Only one country name was used in the Values assessment, and it was written out instead of following the ISO 3166-1 alpha 3 code. More country names were used in tables in the Sustainable Use assessment, and these were also written out.

Data and knowledge from indigenous people and local communities: All the requirements regarding data from Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities were fulfilled; they were informed, consent and approved the representation of their shared knowledge. The terms of agreement on reuse, representation and storage was documented and materials were uploaded to Zotero following these terms.

Disclaimers: Both assessments fulfilled the requirements regarding the disclaimers, and therefore each scored 100% for this section.

Discussion

By using a binary scoring metric, where a requirement is either fulfilled or not, the scoring is objective and simple, but sometimes this way of scoring can be too strict. For example, when scoring references for the presence of a unique identifier, there is no distinction between the lack of one identifier for the whole assessment or hundreds. It might be better to use percentages, for example, if one identifier is missing out of a total 8000 references, the score for this subsection would be 99.9%, which might be more informative than a 0. Also, as there was only one country name used in a table in the Values assessment, which was not written according to the ISO 3166-1 alpha 3 code, its total score would have almost been 5% higher if the right code was used.

Exporting and uploading bibliographies is a gray area. The protocol states that exporting should be done after the Plenary meeting. However, since there are typically six months between the Plenary meeting and the publication of the reports, one could expect that when the reports are published the bibliographies should also be exported and uploaded. This could be made more explicit in the delivery of assessment drafts protocol, as 'after Plenary' leaves ambiguity on when this task should be completed.

It could also be suggested that the subsections should be delivered earlier. For example, it should not be possible that the complete authors list of an assessment is still incomplete after the publication of that assessment. The incongruence between the authors lists provided, the authors listed on the IPBES website and the authors in the citation of the chapter should be prevented.

There were many similarities in the conformity to the protocol between these two assessments. The Values assessment performed better on the delivery of the bibliographic references, while the Sustainable Use assessment met more requirements on the delivery of the figures. There is potential to increase the conformity of the assessments to the delivery protocol without having to edit the assessment reports; by uploading the complete Zotero libraries (without any unused references) and the machine-readable data underlying the tables along with the captions. Additionally, the score of the Sustainable Use assessment could be increased by uploading the interoperable files for the figures as well. When these

files are uploaded, the overall score of the Sustainable Use assessment would be 76.7% (and the overall score of the Values assessment would be 77.2%).

Based on this report, the task force on knowledge and data asked the technical support unit for data to revise the delivery protocol of the assessment drafts to increase its user friendliness, and to add information on the design of the authors list and on the inclusion of identifiers and disclaimers to tables and figures to the technical guidelines on the IPBES ICT portal.

Methods

The most recent version of the delivery protocol of the assessment drafts (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6225417>) includes nine different sections:

- Citations (the citations of the full report, individual chapters, SPM and the authors list)
- Bibliographic references
- Supplementary material
- Delivery of schematic figures
- Delivery of data driven figures
- Delivery of borrowed/adapted figures
- Delivery of tables
- Delivery of data and knowledge form Indigenous people and local communities
- Disclaimers

To avoid a bias towards the figures, the sections delineating the delivery of figures were scored together, so that 7 sections remained. For each subsection, it was evaluated whether the assessment complied with the requirements; and scored with a 1 if all elements of the subsection complied and scored with 0 if any element failed to comply. The total score of each section was transformed into a percentage, with a maximum score of 100%, after which the total score for the assessment was calculated as the average score of the different sections.

The scorecards of the Values and Sustainable Use assessments are attached as supplementary data at the end of this report.

Scorecard for the Values assessment

Description	Responsible Party	Status	Binary	Count	Binary sum	Score
				5	4	80.0%
Suggested citation entire assessment	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Suggested citation SPM	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Suggested citation individual chapters	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Complete list of authors	Assessment TSU	Completed	0			
Citations and list approved by Secretariat	Secretariat	Completed	1			
				6	5	83.3%
Library in Zotero	Secretariat	Completed	1			
Chapters in separate folders in Zotero	Secretariat	Completed	1			
All references cited entered in the right folder	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Unused references are deleted			0			
In-text citations complete and unbroken	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
All entries have an identifier	Assessment TSU	Partially Completed	0			
All references are in APA style	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
				7	6	85.7%
Chapters in docx with connection to Zotero	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Chapters in pdf	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Exported bibliography (.bib)	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Authors' names in correct order	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Related identifier to SPM on Zenodo	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Related identifiers for DMR and data deposit packages	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Data management reports uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	Completed	0			
				19	11	57.9%

Description	Responsible Party	Status	Binary	Count	Binary sum	Score
Original format uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Interoperable and open format uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Native files provided to graphic designer to update colours	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Country borders in line with UN guidelines	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Usage rights (CC0 or CC-BY) assigned	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Caption contains DOI and appropriate disclaimer if applicable	Assessment TSU	Partially Completed	0			
Workflow/scripts used to create figure uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	Partially Completed	0			
Native files provided to graphic designer to update colours	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Country borders in line with UN guidelines	Assessment TSU	Completed	0			
World maps in Robinson projection	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Country names in data follow the ISO 3166-1 alpha 3 code	Assessment TSU	Partially Completed	0			
Usage rights (CC0 or CC-BY) assigned	Assessment TSU	Not Completed	1			
Caption contains DOI and appropriate disclaimer if applicable	Assessment TSU	Completed	0			
Permission to reuse figure is granted from original authors or publisher	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Figure is reviewed	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
High resolution copy uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Proper citation of the figure added to Zotero library	Assessment TSU	Completed	0			
Usage rights (CC0 or CC-BY) assigned	Assessment TSU	Not Completed	0			
Caption contains DOI and appropriate disclaimer if applicable	Assessment TSU	Not Completed	0			
				3	1	33.3%
Original machine-readable data underlying the table along with caption uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			

Description	Responsible Party	Status	Binary	Count	Binary sum	Score
Country names in data follow the ISO 3166-1 alpha 3 code	Assessment TSU		0			
Caption contains DOI and appropriate disclaimer if applicable	Assessment TSU	Partially Completed	0			
				4	4	100.0%
IPLCs are informed and consent	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
IPLCs approve the representation of their shared knowledge	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Terms of agreement on reuse, representation and storage is documented	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Materials are uploaded to Zotero following the agreed terms	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
				3	3	100.0%
Suggested general disclaimer	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Suggested disclaimers for maps, figures and tables are added to captions when necessary	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Suggested disclaimers are checked and approved by Secretariat	Secretariat	Completed	1			
					Final Score	77.2%

Scorecard for the Sustainable Use assessment

Description	Responsible Party	Status	Binary	Count	Binary sum	Score
				5	4	80.0%
Suggested citation entire assessment	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Suggested citation SPM	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Suggested citation individual chapters	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Complete list of authors	Assessment TSU	Completed	0			
Citations and list approved by Secretariat	Secretariat	Completed	1			
				6	3	50.0%
Library in Zotero	Secretariat	Completed	1			
Chapters in separate folders in Zotero	Secretariat	Completed	1			
All references cited entered in the right folder	Assessment TSU	Partially Completed	0			
Unused references are deleted			0			
In-text citations complete and unbroken	Assessment TSU	Not Completed	0			
All entries have an identifier	Assessment TSU	Partially Completed	0			
All references are in APA style	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
				7	6	85.7%
Chapters in docx with connection to Zotero	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Chapters in pdf	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Exported bibliography (.bib)	Assessment TSU		0			
Authors' names in correct order	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Related identifier to SPM on Zenodo	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Related identifiers for DMR and data deposit packages	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Data management reports uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
				19	13	68.4%

Description	Responsible Party	Status	Binary	Count	Binary sum	Score
Original format uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Interoperable and open format uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	Completed	0			
Native files provided to graphic designer to update colours	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Country borders in line with UN guidelines	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Usage rights (CC0 or CC-BY) assigned	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
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Usage rights (CC0 or CC-BY) assigned	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Caption contains DOI and appropriate disclaimer if applicable	Assessment TSU	Completed	0			
				3	0	0.0%
Original machine-readable data underlying the table along with caption uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	Not Completed	0			

Description	Responsible Party	Status	Binary	Count	Binary sum	Score
Country names in data follow the ISO 3166-1 alpha 3 code	Assessment TSU	Not Completed	0			
Caption contains DOI and appropriate disclaimer if applicable	Assessment TSU	Partially Completed	0			
				4	4	100.0%
IPLCs are informed and consent	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
IPLCs approve the representation of their shared knowledge	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Terms of agreement on reuse, representation and storage is documented	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Materials are uploaded to Zotero following the agreed terms	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
				3	3	100.0%
Suggested general disclaimer	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Suggested disclaimers for maps, figures and tables are added to captions when necessary	Assessment TSU	Completed	1			
Suggested disclaimers are checked and approved by Secretariat	Secretariat	Completed	1			
					Final Score	69.2%